

Information Classification & Document Control Policy

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Revision History

Version	Date	Author	Description of Changes
1.0	03/15/2026	Stefan Krauss (ISM)	Initial approved version

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1. Purpose

The purpose of this policy is to establish a structured framework for identifying, classifying, labeling, managing, and controlling the organization's information assets and documented information.

2. Scope

This policy applies to all personnel, departments, and business functions within the organization, as defined in the approved ISMS Scope, and to all information assets and documented information created, received, processed, stored, or transmitted by the organization, regardless of format or location.

3. Roles & Responsibilities

Information user: Information users are responsible for handling information assets in accordance with their assigned classification level and applicable handling requirements.

Their responsibilities include:

- Information is accessed and used only for authorized purposes
- Classification and handling requirements are respected at all times
- Any suspected or actual security incident, including unauthorized access or disclosure, is promptly reported to the appropriate authority

Information/Asset Owner: The Information Asset Owner is responsible for the governance of assigned information assets throughout their lifecycle.

Their responsibilities include:

- Ensuring information assets are correctly classified and appropriately labelled
- Reviewing classifications periodically or when significant changes occur
- Defining access requirements and ensuring appropriate authorization rules are in place
- Ensuring information is managed in accordance with its classification level and organizational policies
- Participating in the review and resolution of information security incidents related to the asset

Information Security Manger: The Information Security Manager is responsible for overseeing the implementation, governance, and continuous improvement of information security practices within the organization.

Responsible for:

- Defining and maintaining the information classification framework and handling standards
- Ensuring consistency of application across the organization
- Providing oversight and guidance on classification-related decisions
- Supporting audits, reviews, and incident investigations

4. Policy

4.1. Information Classification

The organization adopts a three-level information classification schema to ensure that information is protected according to its sensitivity and business impact. All information assets must be classified at the time of creation or receipt based on the potential impact to the organization in the event of unauthorized disclosure, alteration, or loss.

Classification Level	Description & Examples
<p>Public</p>	<p>Information approved for public disclosure. Unauthorized modification may still be controlled, but disclosure does not pose a risk to the organization.</p> <p>Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Marketing materials and brochures - Published blog posts and website content - Public press releases - Job postings
<p>Internal</p>	<p>Information intended for use within the organization. Unauthorized disclosure could cause minor operational, reputational, or competitive impact.</p> <p>Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Internal policies and procedures - Organizational charts - Internal meeting minutes - Non-sensitive operational reports

Confidential	<p>Sensitive information only disclosed to specific individuals or groups. Unauthorized disclosure, alteration, or loss could result in significant legal, financial, operational, or reputational harm.</p> <p>Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Customer data and contracts - Financial records and forecasts - Employee personal information - Security configurations, risk assessments, and audit reports
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4.2. Information Labeling

To ensure consistent handling and protection of information, all information assets must be clearly labeled according to their assigned classification level.

Information shall be labeled according to the following requirements:

- a) **Electronic Documents (Files):** The assigned classification level shall be clearly indicated in the document header or footer. The classification shall also be included in the file name. Where technically supported, document metadata and file properties shall reflect the assigned classification level.
- b) **Physical Documents:** The classification level must be clearly marked at the top or bottom of each page.
- c) **Email Communications:** The classification level must be indicated in the email subject line or as an electronic label. Any attachments must be labeled according to their classification level
- d) **Endpoint Devices and Removable Media:** Laptops, desktops, mobile devices, USB drives, and other removable media must be classified and labeled within the asset inventory.
- e) **Unlabeled information:** Any information that is not explicitly labeled must be treated as Confidential by default until properly classified.

4.3. Document Taxonomy

To ensure consistency, clarity, and proper governance of documented information, the organization adopts a standardized document taxonomy. This taxonomy defines the types of documents used within the organization and clarifies their purpose, level of detail, and intended use.

The following document types are formally recognized:

- a) **Framework:** Strategic and structural documented information that defines the structure, boundaries, governing logic, and decision-making model of the ISMS.
- b) **Policy:** High-level documents that establish management intent, direction, principles, and mandatory requirements. Policies define what must be achieved and provide governance guidance across the organization.
- c) **Standard:** Mandatory technical or operational requirements that support policies by defining specific rules, configurations, or criteria that must be followed.
- d) **Process:** High-level description of an end-to-end set of related activities that transform inputs into outputs to achieve a defined objective.
- e) **Procedure:** A documented sequence of controlled steps required to perform a specific activity within a process.
- f) **Work Instruction:** Detailed, task-specific instructions describing exactly how to perform a defined activity, often including system-level or tool-based specifications.
- g) **Guidance:** Non-mandatory documented recommendations that provide interpretative direction, best practices, or advisory information to support the implementation of policies, standards, processes, procedures, or work instructions.
- h) **Record:** Documented evidence of activities performed, decisions made, or results achieved. Records provide objective evidence of compliance and operational execution.
- i) **Template:** Standardized, pre-approved document formats designed to ensure consistency when creating documented information.

4.4. Document Identification & Versioning

To ensure traceability, consistency, and effective control of documented information, all formal ISMS documents shall follow a standardized identification and versioning convention. Each document must include a document type abbreviation, a unique numerical identifier, and a version number.

a) Document type abbreviations

Document Type	Abbreviation
Framework	FRW
Policy	POL
Standard	STD
Process	PRO
Procedure	PCD
Work Instruction	WKI
Guidance	GDC
Record	REC
Template	TMP

b) Document identification structure

Each controlled document shall be assigned a unique identifier using the structure [TYPE]-[NUMBER] (i.e. POL-01, STD-03, PRO-07)

Numbers shall be assigned sequentially within each document type. Once assigned, a document identifier shall not be reused, even if the document is retired.

Where necessary, departments or functional identifiers may be incorporated to enhance traceability

c) Versioning schema

All controlled documents shall follow a version numbering convention using the format [X].[Y] where:

- X (Major Version) indicates significant changes, structural revisions, scope expansion, or formal re-approval.
- Y (Minor Version) indicates minor edits, clarifications, formatting changes, or non-substantive updates that do not alter the document’s intent.

Examples:

- Version 1.0 – Initial approved release
- Version 1.1 – Minor Revision
- Version 2.0 – Major revision requiring formal approval

d) Identification and version display requirements

The document identifier and version number shall be displayed in the header or footer of the document. Only the latest approved version shall be maintained and made available within official repositories.

4.5. Document Review & Approval

a) Document Review

All controlled governance documents, including policies, standards, processes, and procedures, shall be reviewed at planned intervals and at least annually to ensure continued suitability, adequacy, and effectiveness.

Documents shall also be reviewed whenever significant changes occur that may affect their relevance, including regulatory changes, organizational changes, process modifications, or identified control deficiencies.

Templates must be reviewed periodically to ensure continued alignment with applicable governance documents.

Records are not subject to periodic review requirements but shall be retained and managed in accordance with the organization's retention and document control requirements.

b) Document Approval

All governance documents must be formally approved prior to initial release and following any major revision. Approval shall be granted by the designated document owner and the appropriate authority, as defined by the organization's governance structure.

No governance document shall be considered valid or effective until it has been formally approved and recorded within the controlled document repository.

5. Governance & Compliance

5.1. Communication & Awareness

This policy shall be communicated to all relevant personnel upon publication and whenever significant updates occur.

Awareness activities, including onboarding and periodic training, shall ensure that employees understand their responsibilities regarding information classification and document handling.

The policy shall be made accessible through the organization's official document repository.

5.2. Monitoring & Measurement

Compliance with this policy shall be monitored through periodic reviews, internal audits, and operational checks as part of the Information Security Management System (ISMS).

Key compliance indicators may include adherence to classification rules, correct document labeling, and proper handling of confidential information.

5.3. Exceptions

Any exception to this policy must be formally requested, justified by operational need, and approved by the designated authority or governance body.

Approved exceptions shall be documented and reviewed periodically to ensure they remain valid and appropriately controlled.

5.4. Non-Compliance

Any failure to comply with this policy may result in corrective actions, which may include retraining, access restriction, or disciplinary measures depending on severity and impact.

Non-compliance incidents shall be recorded and addressed through the organization's corrective action process.

5.5. Continual Improvement

This policy shall be reviewed periodically and updated as necessary to reflect changes in business operations, regulatory requirements, risk landscape, or ISMS maturity.

Feedback from audits, incidents, and operational experience may be used to improve the effectiveness of this policy.